

An Investigation into L1 Interference in EFL Students' Writing: Case Study: Al-Baha University, College of Arts & Humanities

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Abstract

This study attempts to identify the interference of L1 in L2 writing among third year of students at the foreign languages, college of Arts & Humanities Al-Baha University. The study adopted a descriptive analytical approach. The study additionally endeavours to identify, classify, and analyse grammatical errors made by the students. Research questions and their results are presented and discussed in order to achieve this goal. The participants were provided with a text to write about within 60 minutes. Based on the study, the students made 235 grammatical errors, with subcategories such as tenses errors (153) and articles (82) serving as examples. When it came to tenses errors, verb agreement errors occurred the most frequently (97%)%, whereas wrong tenses formation errors (56) were made by the respondents (%). The research shows problems in the articles, including subcategories, omitted articles (37), added articles (29), and wrong article selections (16). The primary causes of these kinds of errors in research are represented by L1 interference. Incorrect sentences resulted from the subjects' straight translation of Arabic terms into their English equivalents. According to the study, students should be required to pay more attention to their writing and reading because doing so will help them become more proficient in the English language and prevent them from making grammatical errors in the specified subcategories.

Keywords: EFL learners, Saudi context, error analysis; writing, grammatical errors, interference.

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الملخص

تحاول هذه الدراسة التعرف على تداخل اللغة الإنجليزية (L1) في كتابة اللغة الإنجليزية (L2) لدى طلاب السنة الثالثة لغات بكلية الآداب والعلوم الإنسانية بجامعة الباحة. وقد اعتمدت الدراسة المنهج الوصفي التحليلي. كما سعت الدراسة إلى تحديد وتصنيف وتحليل الأخطاء النحوية التي ارتكبها الطلاب، بالإضافة إلى ذلك سعت الدراسة إلى تحديد وتصنيف وتحليل الأخطاء النحوية التي ارتكبها الطلاب. وتم عرض أسئلة البحث ونتائجها ومناقشتها من أجل تحقيق هذا الهدف. تم تزويد المشاركين بنص للكتابة عنه في غضون 60 دقيقة. واستنادًا إلى الدراسة، فقد ارتكب الطلاب 235 خطأ نحويًا، حيث بلغ عدد الأخطاء النحوية التي ارتكبها الطلاب 235 خطأً نحويًا، وكانت الأخطاء النحوية في الفئات الفرعية مثل أخطاء الأزمنة (153) والمقالات (82) فيما يتعلق بأخطاء الأزمنة، كانت أخطاء اتفاق الأفعال هي الأكثر تكرارًا (97%)، في حين أن أخطاء تشكيل الأزمنة الخاطئة (56%) ارتكبها المبحوثون. كما أظهر البحث وجود أخطاء في المقالات (37%)، وأخطاء في المقالات الفرعية (37%)، وأخطاء في المقالات المضافة (29%)، وأخطاء في اختيار المقالات الخاطئة (16%) وتتمثل الأسباب الرئيسية لهذه الأنواع من الأخطاء في البحث في تداخلات اللغة الإنجليزية (L1) وقد نتجت الجمل غير الصحيحة عن الترجمة المباشرة للمصطلحات العربية إلى ما يقابلها في اللغة الإنجليزية من قبل الطلاب. ووفقًا للدراسة، يجب أن يُطلب من الطلاب الاهتمام أكثر بكتاباتهم وقراءتهم لأن ذلك سيساعدهم على إتقان اللغة الإنجليزية وقيهم من الوقوع في الأخطاء النحوية في الفئات الفرعية المحددة.

الكلمات المفتاحية: متعلمي اللغة الإنجليزية كلغة أجنبية (EFL)، السياق السعودي، تحليل الأخطاء؛ الكتابة،

Introduction

The study of errors is part of the investigation of the process of language learning. It provided us with a picture of the linguistic development of the learner and may give indications to the learning strategies. Also, EA is important in improving teaching methods. That is, it supplies valuable data that can be used in the preparation of teaching materials, textbooks, and assessments, as well as practical applications for language teachers. Corder (1973) suggested five steps to follow during error analysis namely collection of data, identification of errors, description of errors, explanation of errors, and evaluation of errors.

Erdogan. (2005). Points out that: "The study of error is part of the investigation of the process of language learning. In this respect it resembles methodologically the study of the acquisition of the mother tongue. It provides us with a picture of the linguistic development of a learner and may give us indications as to the learning process."

Badr. (2022). Writes: "Making errors is an inevitable part of the learning process, especially when the linguistic systems of L1 and L2 are different. Students can learn from their errors with the help of their teachers' corrective feedback. Errors provide teachers with evidence of the learners' linguistic progress and the linguistic areas that should be reinforced. Al-husban (2018) highlighted the importance of EA in identifying "what students still need to learn; and how to improve their process of learning; the strategies and methods they should use when learning the language; why students add, omit, use wrong forms or words, or disorder structures and sentences; and how to eliminate the use of the mother language in learning a second language" (p. 29). Therefore, errors need to be analyzed to identify their types and sources, and to devise remedial strategies so that students can avoid those errors in advanced levels of language learning.

The theoretical and practical sections make up the two main components of the current research. The study problem, objectives, significance, and research questions are highlighted in the theoretical section. Additionally, the literature study highlights the significance of the EA, models of the error's origins, corrective measures, and EA. Analysis and relevance to the research issue are also provided by previous studies. The practical part addresses the research design, respondents, research instruments, data collection and analysis procedures, and results and discussion. The study ends up with a conclusion summarizing the most important findings and recommendations.

Objectives of the Study

The present study aims at fulfilling the following objectives:

1-To investigate the influence of L1 in the errors writing committed by third year students at Al-Baha University, the College of Arts & Humanities, the Department of Foreign Languages.

2- To describe as well as categorize and analyze the grammatical errors in the writing of first- year female learners in basic English course in preparatory year at Al- Baha University). However, the study aims to analyze the different types of grammatical errors in order to show interlingual errors caused by L1 interference in their written text.

Significance of the Study

The findings of this study would serve as a database for the general language departments, specifically the English Language departments to illustrate writing difficulties caused by first language interference in (L2) writing in order to provide possible solutions. It would be useful for English Foreign Language teachers to consider the issues of first language interference in learners' writing and enable more effective methods of dealing with errors.

Literature Review

Error analysis

Crystal's (1999) (cited in Bain, 2006) defines "error analysis" in language teaching and learning, as a technique for identifying, classifying and systematically interpreting the unacceptable forms produced by someone learning a foreign language, using any of the principles and procedures provided by linguistics. Errors are assumed to reflect, in a systematic way, the level of competence achieved by a learner; they are contrasted with "mistakes," which are performance limitations that a learner would be able to correct".

As stressed by AbiSamra (2003), error analysis is a type of linguistic analysis that focuses on the errors learners make. It consists of a comparison between the errors made in the Target Language (TL) and that TL itself. Pit Corder is the "Father" of Error Analysis (the EA with the "new look"). It was with his article entitled "The significance of Learner Errors" (1967) that EA took a new turn. Errors used to be "flaws" that needed to be eradicated. Corder presented a completely different point of view. He contended that those errors are "important in and of themselves." For learners themselves, errors are 'indispensable,' since the making of errors can be regarded as a device the learner uses in order to learn. In 1994, Gass & Selinker defined errors as "red flags" that provide evidence of the learner's knowledge of the second language.

Researchers are interested in errors because they are believed to contain valuable information on the strategies that people use to acquire a language (Richards, 1974; Taylor, 1975; Dulay and Burt, 1974). Moreover, according to Richards and Sampson (1974, p. 15), "At the level of pragmatic classroom experience, error analysis will continue to provide one means by which the teacher assesses learning and teaching and determines priorities for future effort."

Al-Khresheh. (2016) illustrates: "Up until the late sixties, the prominent theory in the field of SLA or L2 learning was almost behaviouristic, which claimed that the learning was a result of acquiring a set of new language patterns. Hence, L2 errors were considered as only the result of learners' MT habits in the target language (TL hereinafter). Therefore, errors which were not explained based on this assumption will definitely be underestimated. EA, however, deals with "the learners' performance in terms of the cognitive processes they make use of in recognizing or coding the input they receive from the TL".

Mahmoud. (2013] states out that: "Error analysis (EA) is an everlasting endeavor for the simple reason that first, second or foreign language learners, by definition, will continue to commit errors. As Mahmoud (2011, p. 29) says, "Nobody goes from zero competence to full competence in one leap." In the same vein, James (1998, p. 63) states that "as long as there is incompleteness or failure to attain full NS-like knowledge of the TL, there will be EA." Committing errors is a fact of life, so is learning from them. EA is indispensable in language teaching and it is assuming more importance as an index of language learning and communication strategies.

Al-Khresheh. (2016) writes: "According to EA, a great number of errors made by FL learners are similar regardless of their MT. Such errors are caused due intralingual interference or transfer. James (1998) claims that such a type of interference from the structures of the TL itself is the main cause of intralingual errors. These errors can be created without referring to L1 features. Based on this assumption, EA serves two main purposes: the first one is "to provide data from which interference about the nature of the language learning process can be made". The second one "indicates to teachers and curriculum developers which part of the TL students have most difficulty producing correctly and which error types detract most from a learner's ability to communicate".

According to Corder (1973), there are two main objectives of EA: one theoretical and the other being known applied. The theoretical objective checks the validity of the theories such as the theory of transfer. In other words, this objective can help in understanding how and what a FL learner learns whilst studying a FL. On the other hand, the applied objective, "concerns pedagogical purposes" (Mahmoodzadeh, 2012,

p.735). This objective enables learners of L2 to learn their TL more efficiently and effectively by using the previous knowledge of their dialects for pedagogical purposes. Once L2 errors are analysed, the nature of problems and difficulties encountered by language learners will be identified. Identifying such difficulties can therefore help EFL/ESL teachers pinpoint their students' weaknesses and hence revise their teaching methods and learning materials accordingly.

Alolaywi. (2023) stated that: “within SLA, EA was first introduced by Stephen Pit Corder and his colleagues in the late 1970s and became a very popular approach for describing L2 errors (James, 1998). In 1967, Corder argued that L2 errors are significant because they can reflect some of the underlying linguistic rules. The main focus of EA is the actual mistakes made by FL/L2 learners which lately became very popular in the field of applied linguistics. Brown (1994) argued that EA has a great value in classroom research. In fact, the systematic analysis of mistakes made by FL/L2 learners allows determining areas which require reinforcement in teaching. EA was defined by James (1998) as "the process of determining the incidence, nature, causes and consequences of unsuccessful language" (p. 111). In addition, Mahmoodzadeh (2012), defined EA as "a procedure used to identify, categorize, and explain the errors committed by FL/L2 learners".

Dulay et al. (1982). Hold the belief that: “a great deal of errors made by FL learners are similar regardless of their native languages. Such errors are mainly caused by intralingual interference or transfer. James (1998) claimed that such a type of interference from the structures of the target language (TL) itself is the main cause of intralingual errors. Based on this assumption, EA serves two main purposes: first, it provides insights about the types of interference found in second language learners' performances; second, it informs teachers and syllabus designers about the most problematic aspects of the TL that students face difficulty producing”.

According to Corder (1981), there are two main objectives of EA: one theoretical and the other is applied. The theoretical objective aims to check the validity of the theories such as the theory of transfer. In other words, this objective can help in understanding how and what a foreign language (FL) learner learns whilst studying a FL. On the other hand, the applied objective "concerns pedagogical purposes" (Mahmoodzadeh, 2012, p. 735). This objective enables learners of L2 to learn their TL more efficiently and effectively by using the previous knowledge of their linguistic knowledge for pedagogical purposes. In sum, the identification of FL/SL learners' errors and the problems they encounter help EFL/ESL teachers pinpoint.

Lado (1957) says clearly: “Individuals tend to transfer the forms and meanings, and the distribution of forms and meanings of their native language and culture to foreign language and culture to foreign language and culture-both productively when attempting to speak the language and to act in the culture, and receptively when attempting to grasp and understand the language and culture as practiced by natives. Additionally, Transfer is related to the productive and receptive skill either in form or meaning. In other words, EFL learners make transfer both in speaking and writing. Corder. (1975) cited in Hanane (2017) explains transfer saying that, the learner carries the habits of his or her mother tongue into the second language, when there a similarity between learning the TL and the mother tongue. Thus, TL is easy trough the positive transfer, however; when there are differences between learning the TL and the mother tongue, TL would be difficult and it results negative transfer through the occurrence of errors. Temmime (2009) declares that language Transfer has different names used by researchers namely; Selinker (1972) and Kellerman, (1983) called it “Language mixing”, Schacher and Rutherford (1979), and Ringbon (1987) named it “Linguistic interference”. However, Lado (1957) and Selinker (1972) called it “Language transfer”.

The factors of language Interference

According to Zuhri Dj. Et al (2020) there are three factors that cause language interference as follow:

a. The interlingual factor. Interlingual transfer is a significant source for language learners. This concept comes from constructive analysis of the behavioristic school of learning. It stresses upon the negative interference of mother tongue as the only source of errors. The construction ‘I like to read ‘is uttered as ‘I read to like’ by many Hindi Speakers. In Hindi, the verb is pre-positioned while in English it is post positioned. This type of error is the result of negative transfer Of first language rules to target language system.

The over Extension of analogy. Usually, a learner has been wrong in using a vocabulary caused by the similarity of the element between first language and second language, e. g the use of cognate word (the same form of word in two languages with different functions or meanings). The example is the using of month and moon. Indonesian learners may make a mistake by using month to say moon in the space.

b. Transfer of structure. There are two types of transfer according to Dulay et.al (1982:101), positive transfer and negative transfer. Negative transfer refers to those instances of transfer, which result in error because old habitual behavior is different from the new behavior being learned. On the contrary, positive transfer is the correct utterance, because both the first language and second language have the same structure, while the negative transfer from the native language is called interference.

And for the researcher Choubane (2021) source of errors can be classified as follows:

- 1) Language transfer or inter-lingual interference: In this type, errors are caused by native language interference.
- 2) Intra-lingual interference; This kind of interference happens during the learning process of a foreign language at a stage when learners have not really acquired the knowledge.

In order to classify errors, we need a taxonomy. The latter refers to the classification of error according to specific principles. Dulay, Burt, and Krashen (1982) suggested that there are four kinds of error taxonomy; these are:

- 1) *Linguistic Category Classification*. This type of taxonomy carries the specification of error in terms of linguistic categories. Linguistic category involves the language levels of the error, its class, its rank, and its grammatical system.
- 2) *The Surface Structure Taxonomy*. This taxonomy is assigned based on the ways surface structures are altered. This is suitable for analyzing error in writing which is the topic of this research.
- 3) *Comparative error*. This is a taxonomy of error based on comparison between foreign language structures errors and certain other types of construction.
- 4) *Communicative Effect Taxonomy*. It deals with error from the perspective of their effect on listeners. It deals with distinguishing between errors that seem to cause miscommunication and those that do not.

Interference

According to Fries (1945), one of the most important behaviours is that L1 interference is a major issue for learners of second language. In the early 1970s, some researchers began to pay attention to the second language writing process from the written text. They found the writing process in the second language is similar to the writing process in the first language. In addition, certain written features such as planning, revision (Cumming, 1989) and editing can be transferred from writing of the first language to the writing of second language.

An extensive research has already been carried out on first language interference in the target language. According to, Dulay and Burt (1982) they define interference as the automatic transfer of the first language's surface structure to the surface of the target language as a result of habit. Lott (1983: 256) defines interference as 'mistakes in learner's use of foreign language that can be traced back to the mother tongue '. While, Ellis (1997:51) refers to interference as a transfer, which he says is 'the influence of the L1 of the learner on the acquisition of a L2.' He argues that transfer is guided by the perceptions of learners about what can be transferred and their developmental stage in L2 learning. Selinker, (1972),

Seligar, (1988) and Ellis (1997) agrees that when learning a target language, students draw up their own interim rules by using their L1 knowledge, but only if they believe that it will help them with the task of learning or if they have become sufficiently skilled in L2 to be able to transfer.

Previous Studies in Error Analysis

Many studies on error analysis interference between L1 and L2 are common studies that deal exclusively with Arab EFL learners. In reality there are a number of studies done by Arab and Non- Arab researchers on errors committed by L2 learners.

Al-Saggaf, et al. (2022) pointed out that: “researchers believed that students tend to rely on their first language structure when they would like to write or speak in the target language. If the structures are different, there are many errors in L1 so that first language interference in the second language is indicated (Decherts & Dillis, as cited in Bhela, 1999, p.22). A learner has problems in second language such as phonology, vocabulary and grammar due to interference in L2 and L2 habits (Beardsmore, 1982). In addition, Dulat et al. (1982) showed that the acquisition of second language differs from the acquisition of first language, but L1 and L2 students’ errors are very similar. Where Selinker (1983) points out that in learning a second language, there are two types of transfer, which is positive and negative. As for positive transfer, L1 facilitates the acquisition of second language, but as for negative transfer, the first language has a negative impact on L2 and interferes in L1.

Bakr. (2022). *Syntactic Errors in Saudi EFL Learners' Writings: Types, Sources, and Remedial Strategies*, states: “The results showed that among the students' syntactic errors were the inappropriate application of verb forms, subject-verb agreement, the subject, parts of speech, and substitution of content words. The causes of these errors were rooted in the students’ interlingual (first language interference) and intralingual (overgeneralization, inadequate knowledge of second language rules, and inappropriate application of such rules) factors. Detecting and analyzing these actual errors helps teachers, policymakers, and students take immediate actions to remedy them”.

Ghazwan (2021) in his study *Mother Tongue Influence on English Writing: A Study with EFL Learners at the University of Bisha*, stated: “The study revealed that Arabic has both positive and negative influences on the EFL learners' writing in general and on the application of grammar rules by them in particular. To achieve the main objectives of the study, only the negative influence was investigated”.

Ridha (2012) investigated the essay writing errors in English in the works of EFL learners and specified the errors committed by the Iraqi EFL learners, revealing that the major cause of errors is none other than L1 transfer. This is reinforced by the fact that the majority of the learners depend on their L1 when they express their ideas or feelings in L2. The study showed that different kinds of errors could be detected in the writing output of the learners' essays but out of the types of errors, the grammatical errors were considered to be the most frequent and serious ones. It was also found that their writings were highly influenced by the Arabic language. The study also discussed the extraordinary assistance to the field of language where teachers are required to give more attention to interference, influence or transfer phenomena.

Furthermore, all these issues were portions of the key problems which EFL learners have to take in their construction (written or spoken).

Al-Khresheh (2010) reported that Jordanian EFL learners committed a large number of syntactic interlingual errors with regard to word order within simple sentence structure and that these errors were due to the transfer of L1 habits.

Abisamra (2003) specified that “most of the syntactic errors made by Arab EFL learners in their written production are because of the interference of their first language”. The negative transfer might be apparent in cases of dissimilarities between the first language (L1) and the target language (TL), and thus the process of interference or transfer from first language (L1) can be taken as 'a negative matter of transfer'.

Mohammed (2000) states that “as far as the distance between the native and the target language is concerned, learners are often misled by the partial similarities between the two languages.” In the case of Arabic, he indicates that the problem becomes complicated because there are two major varieties of Arabic: Standard Arabic (SA) and Non-Standard Arabic (NSA). The two varieties are linguistically different since they have different structures. He also adds that the “question that has not yet been answered is: which variety of Arabic do learners rely on to learn or use English or any other foreign language.” (ibid: 130). Generally, in reviewing some studies conducted on the syntactic errors committed by Arab EFL learners, Diab (1996) states that most of the syntactic errors committed by EFL Arab learners are attributed to the influence of L1 ‘Arabic’ linguistic structures. He also states that Arab learners depend heavily on their MT in FL. He also asserts that one “common syntactic error that students commit as a result of transfer is faulty word order.” (81).

Noor (1996) presents a justification for analyzing such syntactic errors to better understand strategies utilized by EFL students when they write in a FL. Noor's study is considered a review of the most frequent syntactic errors made by Arab EFL learners native. The important discovery of Noor's study is that the most frequent and common source of error is the influence of the native language in processing English syntactic structures.

Research Method

6.1. Sampling and Participants

The study sample consists of 25 Saudi EFL students from the Department of English at Al-Baha University, Saudi Arabia. Those students were enrolled in a writing course as part of their study plan in the Foreign Language Department, College of Arts & Humanities. The students were asked to write an essay of no less than 50 words on one of the following topics: "Journey to Jeddah". The duration of the test was two hours, and the required paragraphs length is a minimum of 800 words. The data was collected during the first semester of the academic year 2023-2024. The corpus used in this study is collected from the written paragraphs of 25 students.

Data Analysis and Discussion

The data collected for this study were analyzed in accordance with Chanquoy's (2001) paradigm of writing errors. These errors were classified into the following:

this category tackles the errors which are related. (2) Tenses errors: this category deals with the errors related to verb-subject agreement and wrong formation of tenses. (3) Articles: this category aims to identify errors related to articles. The data analysis calculations from the entire current research paper are displayed in the tables below, which demonstrate the many cohesive device types that the students utilized in their written essays. Every grammatical error in the students' essays has its data analysis calculated by the researcher.

Table [1-1] Shows Students Grammatical Errors in Number

No	Type of Error	Number of Inappropriate Uses
1	Grammar	235

Table 1 indicates that there were 235 instances of students using grammar incorrectly.

Table [1-1-2] Displays the Students' Grammatical Subcategory Errors in Number and Percentage

No	Type of Grammatical Errors	Number of Inappropriate Uses	
1	Tenses	153	
2	Articles	82	
	Total	235	

The researcher presents the frequency of grammar errors utilized, including tenses and articles. The following were the outcomes of the data analysis that was obtained: According to the analysis, tenses errors were the highest frequency (153), followed by articles [82].

Table [-3] Displays the Students' Tenses' Subcategory Errors in Number and Percentage

No	Type of Tenses Errors	Number of Inappropriate Uses	
1	Subject-Verb Agreement	97	
2	Wrong formation of tenses	56	
	Total	153	

The frequency with which the students' written essays tenses displayed in the above table, shows two different kinds of tenses errors that are employed: subject-verb agreement, and wrong formation of tenses.

13- I student at Al-Baha University.

14- I hope you with me in the journey.

The participants' errors in the above two examples is verb "be". In Arabic there are no parallel to 'is' and 'were', so the Arab learner of English can likely say: 'I student', or 'Ahmed teacher', or what your name? instead of: "I am student", "Ahmed is a teacher", "what is your name?"

14- I* go to Jeddah three days ago.

16- People in Jeddah lives in high buildings.

17- While in Jeddah I wrote a letter to my father last week.

18- We* seed all the tourist sites of Jeddah.

I was* saw camels and donkeys. Redundant use of 'be'

I saw many place in Jeddah ---- the participants deleted the plural 's' morpheme

12- The journey to Jeddah National Park was *a enjoyable journey _ an.

Misuse of Present tense: Students tended to switch between different present tenses such as mixing between present simple and continuous: for example: I am study English from the intermediate school.

Misuse of Future tense: The following examples explain some of the students' errors when it came to the future tense, with many of them mixing up the present and the future tense in the third part of the interview, when students were asked to talk about their future plans, such as: • I set front of the TV, I'll be online

Tense: Present

Aspect: Perfect Progressive

Students' errors:

- I spending. Type: Omission. I have been spending ...
- I have been spend. Type: misformation.
- I'm been spending. Type: misformation.

Tense: Present

Aspect: Simple

Expected answer: Khalid travels every morning to Riyadh.

Students' errors:

- Khalid travel every morning to Riyadh. Type: Omission. Khalid travels every morning to Riyadh.

This type of error is a common one among Saudi students learning English as a foreign language. It can be explained as an intralingual error which is overcome with time and practice.

Tense: Present

Aspect: Progressive

I travelling now. I am traveling now ...

Aspect: Perfect

- You written. Type: Omission. You haven't written
- . Type: misformation.
- You don't have goed. You don't have gone. Type: misformation.

Tense: Future

Aspect: Simple

Expected answer: When will you come to Jeddah?

Students' errors:

- When you come? Type: omission

- When you will come? Type: misordering.

In this tense, the most frequent errors are not really errors in the formation of the future tense, but errors in the correct formation of the simple present which students chose as the correct tense according to the context.

Aspect: Past Perfect

- I have never saw. Type: misformation: I had never seen.

Table [-4] displays the students' articles subcategory errors in number and percentage

No	Type of Articles Errors	Number of Inappropriate Uses	
1	Omission of article	37	
2	Addition of article	29	
3	Wrong choice of article	16	
	Total	82	

The frequency with which the students' written essays articles displayed in the above table, shows three different kinds of articles errors that are employed: Omission of article, addition of article, and wrong choice of article.

Jeddah seaport is largest seaport in Arab world

Jeddah is most crowded city in Saudi Arabia.

The interference of the students' mother tongue led the respondents in *Jeddah seaport is largest seaport in Arab world* and *Jeddah is most crowded city in Saudi Arabia*, respectively to omit the definite article 'the' because in Arabic zero article is used before superlative, where the definite article is not present. This contrary to what it is in English where the language requires the use of the definite article before superlative.

Indefinite a/an omission

Indefinite 'a' used to be omitted before singular consonant nouns. To exemplify from the participants' production, the following items:

The journey to Jeddah was very beautiful journey /a

While in Jeddah I saw interesting places/an

b-addition of article

as the performance of the participants shows unwanted articles added. The unneeded addition represented in the redundancy of definite and indefinite article alike. To prove this fact, the researcher cited these examples:

My friend the journey was in the Sunday.

I travelled to Jeddah by a bus.

The addition of the unnecessary articles as cited in the examples above led to obscurity in meaning and broken down in communication.

Wrong choice of articles

The wrong choice of articles it can introduced as in:

While in Jeddah and with my friend we visited the museum. A visit was so interesting.

Jeddah beach made the city the famous city in the Kingdom.

It is obvious that the participants did not know the rule which says the definite article 'the' is used before noun that is mentioned for the second time. *So, the student in While in Jeddah and with my friend we visited the museum. A visit was so interesting*, replaced the definite article 'the' used the indefinite article 'a'. whereas, the student *Jeddah beach made the city the famous city in the Kingdom*, ignores the rule of using 'a' before singular count nouns.

Table 4.2.1 shows examples of tenses error that were extracted from the written samples of the students. The most frequent grammar error that occurred in writing was tenses error. Due to non-existed tenses in Arabic language, the participants were unable to differentiate between the present tense and past tense in Arabic language. In Arabic language, the 'be' verbs of past tense do not exist to be added in each sentence to show that it had already happened.

Findings of the Study

The findings of the study revealed that third-year students at the Department of Foreign Languages, College of Arts and Humanities, Al-Baha University, encountered considerable difficulties in English writing as a result of both interlingual and intralingual factors. The analysis of the students' written compositions identified a total of 235 grammatical errors, which were classified into two major categories: tense errors (153) and article errors (82). Tense errors constituted the largest proportion of the errors and demonstrated that students faced substantial challenges in mastering the English tense system. The most frequent errors involved subject-verb agreement, omission or misuse of the verb *be*, incorrect tense formation, confusion between different aspects of the present tense, and misuse of future tense structures.

These errors indicate that many students had difficulty applying English grammatical rules accurately and frequently transferred Arabic language patterns into their English writing.

The analysis further revealed that article usage posed another significant challenge for the participants. Students frequently omitted definite and indefinite articles, added unnecessary articles, or selected incorrect articles. The omission of articles was the most common article-related error, particularly in contexts where English requires the definite article before superlative adjectives or the indefinite article before singular countable nouns. Such errors reflect the influence of Arabic, whose article system differs considerably from that of English. The addition of unnecessary articles and the incorrect selection between definite and indefinite articles also demonstrated a lack of mastery of English article rules and their contextual usage.

Moreover, the findings suggest that mother-tongue interference was a major source of grammatical errors. Many students appeared to translate Arabic structures directly into English, resulting in omissions of auxiliary verbs, incorrect tense forms, and inappropriate article usage. However, the study also found evidence of intralingual errors resulting from overgeneralization and incomplete learning of English grammar. Examples such as *writed* instead of *wrote* and *seed* instead of *saw* indicate that some errors were caused by learners' attempts to apply English grammatical rules without full knowledge of their exceptions. Therefore, the findings demonstrate that both first-language interference and insufficient mastery of English grammatical structures contributed significantly to the students' writing difficulties.

Overall, the study confirms that tense usage and article selection are among the most problematic grammatical areas for Saudi EFL learners. The high frequency of these errors highlights the need for greater instructional focus on English grammar, particularly in areas where Arabic and English differ substantially. The findings further suggest that increased practice in writing, exposure to authentic English texts, and explicit instruction on problematic grammatical structures may help students reduce such errors and improve their overall writing proficiency.

Conclusion

This study investigated the influence of first language (L1) interference on second language (L2) writing among third-year students in the Department of Foreign Languages, College of Arts and Humanities, Al-Baha University. The study aimed to identify, classify, and analyze the grammatical errors that students make in their English writing and to determine the extent to which these errors are influenced by Arabic

language structures. Using a descriptive-analytical approach, the researcher analyzed students' written compositions and categorized the errors according to their grammatical features.

The findings revealed that grammatical errors remain a major challenge for Saudi EFL learners. A total of 235 grammatical errors were identified, indicating that the participants still encounter considerable difficulties in producing grammatically accurate written English despite their advanced level of study. The analysis demonstrated that tense errors were the most frequent category, accounting for 153 errors, while article errors accounted for 82 errors. These findings suggest that the English tense system and article usage continue to represent problematic areas for Arabic-speaking learners of English.

The results further showed that subject–verb agreement errors and incorrect tense formation were the most common tense-related problems. Students frequently omitted auxiliary verbs, misused the verb *be*, confused present and past tense forms, and experienced difficulty in using English perfect and progressive aspects. Such errors reflect the structural differences between Arabic and English, particularly in relation to tense marking and auxiliary verb usage. Since Arabic does not always require equivalent grammatical structures, many students transferred Arabic patterns directly into English, resulting in inaccurate sentence construction.

Similarly, article errors demonstrated the considerable influence of Arabic on English writing. The omission of definite and indefinite articles was the most common article-related error, followed by article addition and incorrect article selection. These difficulties can be attributed to the differences between the Arabic and English article systems. As a result, students often relied on Arabic linguistic patterns when producing English sentences, leading to frequent grammatical inaccuracies.

The study also revealed that not all errors were solely the result of mother-tongue interference. Some errors appeared to stem from intralingual factors, including overgeneralization of grammatical rules and incomplete mastery of English language structures. Examples such as *writed* instead of *wrote* and *seed* instead of *saw* indicate that learners attempted to apply regular grammatical rules to irregular forms. Therefore, the findings suggest that both interlingual transfer and intralingual processes contribute to the grammatical difficulties experienced by Saudi EFL learners.

The significance of this study lies in its contribution to understanding the specific grammatical challenges faced by university students learning English as a foreign language. By identifying the most frequent error types and their probable causes, the study provides valuable insights for language instructors, curriculum designers, and researchers. The findings highlight the necessity of addressing areas where Arabic and English differ substantially, particularly in tense usage, subject–verb agreement, auxiliary verbs, and article systems.

Based on these findings, it is recommended that English language instructors devote greater attention to explicit grammar instruction and contrastive analysis between Arabic and English. Writing courses should incorporate regular error-analysis activities, guided writing practice, and corrective feedback that focuses on recurrent grammatical problems. Furthermore, students should be encouraged to engage in extensive reading and frequent writing practice, as increased exposure to authentic English language use can help reduce the negative effects of first-language interference and improve overall writing proficiency.

In conclusion, the study confirms that first-language interference remains a significant source of grammatical errors in the writing of Saudi EFL learners. Although learners encounter difficulties arising from both interlingual and intralingual factors, the influence of Arabic linguistic structures continues to play a major role in shaping students' written English. Addressing these challenges through targeted pedagogical strategies can contribute significantly to improving learners' grammatical accuracy and overall communicative competence in English.

References

- Abdulmoneim Mahmoud. (2013). Errors in error analyses. Volume 20 No. 1 January 2013 TESOL Arabia Perspectives www.tesolarabia.org.
- Abi Samra, N. (2003). *An analysis of errors in Arabic speakers' English writings: Investigating writing problems among Palestinian students studying English as a foreign language* (Unpublished doctoral dissertation). American University of Beirut.
- Ahmed Al-Sof, B. B. M. (2022). Syntactic errors in Saudi EFL learners' writings: Types, sources, and remedial strategies. *Journal of Research in Language & Translation*, 2(1).
- Al-Khresheh, M. (2010). Interlingual interference in the English language word order structure of Jordanian EFL learners. *European Journal of Social Sciences*, 16(1), 106–113.
- Al-Khresheh, M. H. (2015). A review study of interlanguage theory. *International Journal of Applied Linguistics and English Literature*, 4(3), 123–131.
- Al-Khresheh, M. H. (2016). A review study of error analysis theory. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Research*, 2.
- Al-Saggaf, M. A., et al. (2022). L1 interference in L2 writing: A study on Year 3 BTEFL students. *International Journal of Linguistics and Translation Studies*, 3(2).
- Byrne, D. (1988). The significance of learners' errors. In J. C. Richards (Ed.), *Error analysis: Perspectives on second language acquisition* (pp. 19–27). Longman.
- Choubane, S. (2021). An investigation of the influence of L1 on EFL students' paragraph writing: Case of first-year English language students at Setif 2 University. *Algerian Journal of Manuscripts*, 17(Special Issue), 120–133.
- Corder, S. P. (1967). The significance of learners' errors. Reprinted in J. C. Richards (Ed.), *Error analysis: Perspectives on second language acquisition*. Longman.
- Corder, S. P. (1971). Idiosyncratic errors and error analysis. In J. C. Richards (Ed.), *Error analysis: Perspectives on second language acquisition*. Longman.
- Corder, S. P. (1974). *Error analysis*. Oxford University Press.
- Corder, S. P. (1981). *Error analysis and interlanguage*. Oxford University Press.
- Diab, N. (1996). The transfer of Arabic in the English writings of Lebanese students. *These*, 18(1), 71–83.

- Dulay, H., Burt, M., & Krashen, S. (1982). *Language two*. Oxford University Press.
- Erdoğan, V. (2005). Contribution of error analysis to foreign language teaching. *Mersin University Journal of the Faculty of Education*, 1(2), 261–270.
- Mohamed, A. H., & Omar, M. R. (1999). Syntax as a marker of rhetorical organization in written texts: Arabic and English. *IRAL*, 37(4), 291–305.
- Mohammed, A. (2004). Interlingual transfer in foreign language learning: A critical survey of the second half of the past century. *The Educational Journal*, 20(77).
- Mohammed, G. M. S. (2021). Mother tongue influence on English writing: A study with EFL learners at the University of Bisha. *Asian ESP Journal*, 17(3.2).
- Muliyana, M. Z. D., et al. (2020). Language interference in ELT writing class. *International Journal of Research on English Teaching and Applied Linguistics*, 1(2).
- Noor, H. H. (1996). English syntactic errors by Arabic-speaking learners: Reviewed. In *The Fourth International Symposium on Language and Linguistics* (pp. 1441–1465). Institute of Language and Culture for Rural Development, Mahidol University.
- Richards, J. C. (Ed.). (1974). *Error analysis: Perspectives on second language acquisition*. Longman.
- Selinker, L. (1974). Interlanguage. In J. C. Richards (Ed.), *Error analysis: Perspectives on second language acquisition* (pp. 31–54). Longman.
- Serhani, M. (2017). *The impact of first language “negative transfer” on EFL learners’ writing proficiency: The case of second year LMD students of English at the University of 8 Mai 1945, Guelma* (Master’s dissertation).
- Shahrani, H. M. A. (2018). Mother tongue interference: A study of interlingual errors in the written performance of the EFL preparatory year female students at Al-Baha University in Saudi Arabia. *Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 2(2).